

The Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Sustainable Development

Country Report of Peru

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This Country Report is the result of intense collaborative work between Peru's Ministry of Sport (IPD) and the international cooperation consortium comprising the Ibero-American Sports Council (CID), UNESCO, the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF), and the Research Centre in Sports Science of the King Juan Carlos University (CIDE).

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Introduction

By mandate of the Ministers and High Authorities of Sport of Ibero-America, in 2022, the Ibero-American Council of Sport (CID), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), and the German Development Cooperation – GIZ, formed a consortium to develop the first common indicators to measure the impact of sport and physical activity on sustainable development in the Ibero-American region. Subsequently, in 2023, the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF) and the Rey Juan Carlos University of Spain joined the consortium.

The Ibero-American sport indicators aim to provide countries with regular, standardised and comparable information on the impact of sport on the various dimensions of sustainable development, as well as the periodic evaluation of policies that allows for the identification of opportunities for improvement and the support of achievements and results. Additionally, the indicators seek to facilitate the measurement of the social return on sport, ultimately encouraging increased investment in sport and physical activity. At the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, in May 2023, the unanimous approval was given for the creation of 12 indicators and four key data points to be implemented across the region. Furthermore, it was agreed to conduct a pilot implementation of these indicators in a group of applicant countries.

The objective of the pilot study was to validate the relevance and applicability of the indicators so that they may be scaled up to the entire region, as well as to carry out an initial calculation of those for which data is available according to existing information sources. Based on this, a report would be produced for each country on the status of the indicators, along with a cross-cutting document outlining the results and lessons learned.

A first phase of the pilot was conducted in Chile, Costa Rica and Ecuador between August 2023 and March 2024, and its results were presented at the XXX General Assembly of the CID in Washington, D.C. A second phase of the pilot was implemented in Colombia and Peru between September 2024 and March 2025, and its results are expected to be presented at the XXXI General Assembly of the CID.

This document corresponds to the Peru Country Report, which analyses the status of the indicators and the scope of information sources, as well as the challenges for their implementation in line with the country's institutional, cultural and socio-economic context. Likewise, it establishes the connection between the indicators and the national policies and programmes for sport and physical activity, and includes some lessons learned during the implementation of the pilot.

The Peru Country Report is complemented by the technical data sheets of the indicators whose values could be calculated during the pilot, as well as by the general manual for the preparation of technical data sheets for those indicators whose values could not be estimated at this stage due to a lack of available data. The technical data sheets provide a detailed description of the main characteristics of each indicator and are intended to facilitate their correct interpretation, implementation and scalability. Likewise, these data sheets are essential for replicating calculations and promoting discussion among experts.

In the same vein, it is also recommended to consult the Report on Results and Lessons Learned from the Second Phase of the Pilot, which presents an overview of the progress made by the participating countries and the outcome of the technical assessment of the indicators by those countries. In addition, it includes a list of lessons learned and recommendations for the general implementation of the indicators across the region.

Finally, the international cooperation consortium comprised of the CID, UNESCO, GIZ, CAF, and the Rey Juan Carlos University would like to express special gratitude to the Internal Working Group on Physical Activity of the Colombian Ministry of Sport, whose technical team was strongly involved and committed to the development of this document.

I. Country Context

Sport and physical activity observed in the countries are closely related to their social, cultural, and economic context, as well as to the visions and priorities reflected in their strategic policies and programs for the sector. Therefore, to better understand the status of the indicators, it is important to provide country-specific information that allows us to more precisely identify the major challenges and opportunities for consolidating a common set of indicators for the Ibero-American region.

Peru is characterized by a vast territorial expanse (1,285,215 km²) with three distinctive geographic regions: Coast, Highlands, and Jungle (Gobierno de Perú, 2024), which contain significant orographic, demographic, social, and cultural differences among communities. This, in turn, entails a wide variety of situations and challenges for physical activity and sports.

Furthermore, Peru is a developing country with an economy that has experienced sustained growth in the last two decades, thanks primarily to mining, agriculture, and tourism. However, significant social and economic inequalities persist, with a significant gap between urban and rural areas. Poverty affected 29% of the population in 2023 (INEI, 2024), especially in the Andean and Amazonian regions, where access to resources and services is limited.

These inequalities, among others, have a direct influence on participation in physical activity and sport. In urban areas, the middle and upper classes tend to have greater access to sports facilities, clubs and private gyms. In contrast, in rural and low-income areas, infrastructure is scarce or non-existent, limiting opportunities for both informal and organised sport. Furthermore, the cost of sports equipment and access to specialised training act as barriers preventing a large segment of the population from engaging in sport or physical activity.

According to the National Institute of Statistics and Informatics (INEI), in 2023 the average age of the population was 33.6 years (INEI, 2023). This means that the Peruvian population is considered young. However, the ageing rate has increased, presenting additional challenges in terms of public health and physical activity aimed at this demographic segment. Migration from rural to urban areas has led to rapid urban expansion, particularly in Lima, which has a high population density. This urbanisation, combined with sedentary lifestyles and a rise in non-communicable diseases (such as obesity and diabetes), has increased the need to promote active lifestyles.

Peru has a rich cultural diversity, with a heritage that includes Indigenous, Afro-Peruvian and mestizo traditions. The culture of sport—especially football—holds a central place in the social life of many Peruvians. However, other disciplines such as volleyball, surfing and martial arts are also popular. Rural communities, in particular, have their own forms of physical activity that are linked to their traditions and beliefs. For example, ritual dances are both a physical and spiritual form of expression for them. These dances are connected to festivities dedicated to Andean deities. Similarly, traditional games involving endurance and physical skill are common among young people.

Culturally, engagement in physical activity and sport is also shaped by social perceptions of the body, health and leisure. Although awareness of the benefits of physical activity is growing, sedentary behaviour has become increasingly ingrained—partly due to lifestyle changes associated with urbanisation and technology.

The “National Policy on Physical Activity, Recreation, Sport and Physical Education of Peru”, enacted through “Supreme Decree No. 014-2022-MINEDU”, establishes a comprehensive vision for the development of sport and physical activity in the country, with an inclusive and accessible approach for

all. Through the promotion of physical activity at different levels and the improvement of sports infrastructure, the policy seeks not only to enhance the population's health and well-being, but also to contribute to the social, educational and economic development of the nation, positioning sport as a key tool in building a more active, healthy and cohesive society.

This policy defines clear objectives aimed at achieving a desired future situation:

“By 2030, 50% of the Peruvian population, of all ages, will engage in physical, recreational and sporting activities for an active and healthy life.”

To measure progress and assess the achievement of the prioritised objectives, a set of quantitative indicators has been established for each goal, which must be met by the various actors within the “National Sports System (SISDEN)”, according to their respective responsibilities.

The “Peruvian Institute of Sport (IPD)” serves as the governing body of the National Sports System (SISDEN). Among its main roles are:

- Providing strategic leadership and management of SISDEN to ensure coordination among its actors.
- Developing infrastructure and sports equipment for high-performance competition in coordination with the “National Sports Federations”.
- Providing technical advice and support to strengthen the organisations that form part of SISDEN.
- Supporting, recognising and encouraging high-performance athletes in accordance with the legal provisions governing the field.
- Managing SISDEN's statistical information and monitoring, evaluating and disseminating key performance indicators.
- Promoting the participation of people with disabilities in both general and specialised sporting activities.

The Peruvian Institute of Sport (IPD) has carried out a range of activities aimed at promoting sport and physical activity nationwide, achieving a positive impact on the population. One of the most notable initiatives is “Sports massification”, which has benefited a total of 461,332 people across the country. Among the most prominent programmes and initiatives under this activity is the “Activate con el IPD” programme, which reached 126,524 people in schools, local governments, ministries and other institutions.

The celebration of key dates such as “World Physical Activity Day”, “Challenge Day”, and “National Sports Day” benefited more than 171,000 people. These events not only aim to encourage physical activity but also to raise public awareness about the benefits of leading an active lifestyle.

The IPD has also invested in the training of sports professionals to strengthen the skills of practitioners and technical staff nationwide. In 2023, a total of 57 training sessions were conducted, benefiting 4,990 participants through face-to-face, virtual and blended learning formats.

In the educational field, the IPD oversees the sports component of the Experimental Sports Educational Centre (CEDE) “Julia Sánchez Deza”, which provides schooling for children and adolescents with sporting talent, allowing them to combine academic education with athletic development.

In terms of high-performance sports, in 2023, a total of 41 Peruvian delegations participated in 331 international events, winning 639 gold medals, 611 silver medals, and 827 bronze medals.

Another significant achievement has been the execution of projects and the search for investment to improve sports infrastructure nationwide, as well as the strengthening of institutional ties with international governmental and non-governmental organizations. During 2023, the IPD invested S/ 4,492,351.43 to improve sports infrastructure. This investment contributed to the adaptation of facilities for the practice of physical, recreational, and sports activities, promoting the widespread participation of sports and the performance of highly competitive athletes.

Likewise, a strategic action of the IPD is the Peruvian Sports Observatory (ODP). Its creation responds to a critical need to institutionalize the collection, generation, analysis, and dissemination of sports data in the country, with the aim of improving the development of Peruvian sports at various levels and providing input for decision-making in sports policies and sports management in general.

In Peru, policies aimed at promoting sports and physical activity are geared toward improving the population's quality of life and strengthening sports infrastructure, seeking not only widespread sports practice but also high performance among athletes. One of the main tools is Budget Program 0101, which aims to increase the practice of physical, sports, and recreational activities among the Peruvian population. Through this program, the government allows for the programming of resources to improve sports infrastructure and ensure that citizens have access to adequate facilities for their physical development. In addition, it promotes the creation of accessible spaces in various locations.

II. Indicators Creation Process

The creation and implementation of the pilot indicators formally began in 2022, when, during the XXVIII General Assembly of the CID (Consejo Iberoamericano del Deporte), the Ministers and High Authorities of Sport of Ibero-America issued a mandate for their development. After three years, following an extensive participatory analysis process for their design and review, the indicators have been applied in pilot studies across five countries in the region—Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador and Peru—with encouraging results towards their broader implementation across Ibero-America. Figure 1 presents the timeline of the main political and technical milestones in the development of the indicators.

The process of identifying the indicators began with a review of specialised literature on existing sport indicators and their relationship with sustainable development (SGI-CID, 2019; Commonwealth, 2020a, 2020b, 2019; UNESCO, 2018 and 2017), which served as the basis for a conceptual and normative framework document.

Subsequently, an exploratory online questionnaire was conducted to identify priority themes for indicator measurement in the region, with the participation of 83 experts from 22 countries. Of these, 44% worked in government, 11% in academia, 10% in NGOs, 10% in international organisations, 8% in sports training schools, 4% in sports clubs, and 13% in other sectors.

Following this, the consortium—composed of the CID, UNESCO and GIZ—proposed an initial set of 60 indicators to be examined through a broad participatory analysis process aimed at selecting a priority set of indicators for regional implementation. This process included 18 semi-structured interviews with academics, government officials and representatives from international organisations (October–November 2022), during which participants provided recommendations and identified the most relevant and feasible indicators to implement.

In addition, two virtual focus groups were held in November 2022 with 22 government technical representatives, during which participants ranked the indicators according to their importance for development, conceptual clarity and data availability for calculation. A virtual meeting for preliminary validation of the indicators was also held in November 2022, with the participation of 37 government representatives from 17 countries in the region.

Based on the findings from these exercises and considering technical criteria and regional thematic interests, the consortium selected 13 indicators and 4 key data points for a final assessment and selection workshop, held in Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia, in March 2023. During this in-person workshop, participants analysed the clarity, relevance, feasibility and cost-effectiveness of the indicators, establishing their importance and level of feasibility for implementation. As a result of this workshop, the consortium decided to remove one indicator due to its conceptual complexity and the technical and budgetary challenges involved in producing the necessary statistical data for its calculation.

Figure 1. Timeline of the Indicators Creation Process

Subsequently, the 12 indicators and four key data points were approved by the region's ministries and senior sports authorities at the XXIX CID General Assembly in Cartagena de Indias, Colombia, in May 2023. They also established a mandate for the pilot in a sample of CID member countries.

Thus, in June 2023, the Consortium issued a call to CID member countries to participate in the pilot based on certain basic technical criteria and institutional commitments from the applicant countries.

After analyzing the applications, the countries were notified. The first phase of implementation would involve the participation of Chile, Costa Rica and Ecuador, and the second phase, Colombia and Peru.

The objective of the pilot was to validate the relevance and applicability of the indicators for scaling across the region, as well as to conduct an initial assessment of them where possible based on available information sources. The pilot produced a report for each country on the status of the indicators, as well as a cross-cutting document on the results and lessons learned.

A first phase of the pilot was carried out in Chile, Costa Rica, and Ecuador between August 2023 and March 2024, and its results were presented at the 30th CID General Assembly in Washington, DC. A second phase of the pilot was implemented in Colombia and Peru between September 2024 and March 2025, and its results are also expected to be presented at the 31st CID General Assembly.

III. General Progress Overview

Regarding Peru's results in implementing the indicators, the country managed to calculate the values for four of the 12 indicators (33.3%) and the total for the four key data points. A summary of these achievements is shown in Table 2. The first column shows the name of the data point or indicator, the second its value, and the third important observations, which will be addressed in greater detail in the next section.

Table 1. Results of the Implementation of Key Data Points and Indicators in the Pilot

Key Data	Value	Observations
1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes"
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Autonomous body attached to the Ministry of Education	
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes"
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Partially	
Indicators	Value	Context
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity disaggregated by levels of governance	0.08%	
- Percentage of regional governments' public budgets invested in the national entity for sport and physical activity	0.12%	
- Percentage of local governments' public budgets invested in the national entity for sport and physical activity	3.05%	
- Percentage of the total national public budget invested in the national entity for sport and physical activity.	0.57%	
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	Not Available	Necessary to develop a satellite account
3. Percentage of the population over 14 years old sufficiently physically active disaggregated by gender	42.0%	Own Estimation
4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	8.8%	Own Estimation using GOPA methodology
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	Not Available	Necessary to have a school census or survey
6. Percentage of school students sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	Not Available	
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	Not Available	
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	22.0%	
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old	Not Available	Necessary to develop a survey
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	Not Available	
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	Not Available	Necessary to develop a survey
12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	Not Available	

It is important to note that some of the data and indicator names differ slightly from those in the generic list of indicators due to countries using different age ranges in their survey target populations and/or different accounting and government management categories. For this reason, some indicators are not strictly comparable across countries, which requires future harmonization efforts in some areas.

IV. Situation of Key Data Points and Indicators

This section presents the status of the value of the key data and indicators, regardless of whether it was possible to calculate their value during the pilot. For each data item and indicator, a brief justification or relevance for its calculation, its value, and the main source of information are presented. Likewise, the country's position or perspective on the status of the indicators and the policies it is implementing or plans to implement to strengthen their compliance are presented. In some cases, the country also presents suggestions for improving the indicator approach, or, where applicable, their limitations.

Details for calculating the indicators, their breakdown into sub-indicators, and the reference concepts used can be found in the country's fact sheets document for indicators with a value; and in the general guide for preparing fact sheets for indicators without a value. The main information fields contained in the fact sheets are: indicator definition, justification, calculation method, unit of measurement, year, periodicity, geographic coverage, sources of information, and concepts used, among others.

Key Data Point 1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age

Key Data Point with Value

To support evidence for the design of policies and programs for sport and physical activity, representative, reliable, and periodic data are essential. Having a national survey on sports practice and physical activity, disaggregated by gender and age groups, is the first step toward building basic indicators in this area, such as the percentage of the population sufficiently physically active and the existing gaps by gender or age group.

The reference survey for generating information on sport and physical activity in Peru is the "National Survey of Physical Activity and Healthy Lifestyle Habits," conducted in 2021. Despite the survey's significant scope, it was not designed to capture gender and age group differences in a representative manner. This circumstance, coupled with the fact that the microdata and basic tabulated survey results are not directly available to the public (although they can be requested via the public information access process), makes the data's value "partially."

Another important limitation of the reference survey is that it lacks information on the time the population spends engaged in physical activity, making it impossible to use its data to calculate the "Percentage of the population sufficiently physically active" indicator, one of the most important in the Ibero-American set of sports indicators.

Table 2. Basic Features of the Key Data Point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	2021	Instituto Peruano del Deporte (2021)

Country's Positioning

The main objective of the "2021 National Survey of Physical Activity and Healthy Living Habits" was to obtain detailed information on the physical activity levels and healthy living habits of the Peruvian population aged 18 to 70, of both genders and all socioeconomic levels (NSE), residing in urban and rural areas. Additionally, people with disabilities were included to understand their level of participation in physical activities and access to healthy living practices.

The Peruvian Sports Institute (IPD) has recognized the importance of a new national survey on sport, physical activity, and healthy living habits that would provide more detailed and reliable data for analysis and decision-making in public policy. This survey should include disaggregations by variables such as age, sex, socioeconomic level, geographic region, among others, to ensure international comparability of the indicators and provide accurate information that promotes the promotion of physical activity and health in the country.

To implement this survey, a series of specific steps must be followed, ranging from securing funding to its design and effective execution. The first stage consists of allocating the required budget for the survey. This source of funding will come from the Peruvian Sports Observatory, which is responsible for the collection, generation, analysis, and dissemination of sports data in the country, with the goal of improving the development of Peruvian sports at various levels.

Once funding is secured, the next step is the survey design. To achieve this, a multidisciplinary team must be formed that includes experts in statistics, public health, sports, sociology, and other relevant fields. This team will be responsible for defining the objective of the survey, the key questions to be included, and the data collection methodologies. It will be necessary to evaluate whether the survey will be outsourced to a national or international specialist company, or whether the IPD itself will conduct it.

Data Key Point 2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity

Key Data Point with Value

The governmental status of the national governing body for sport and physical activity determines its capacity to establish regulations, design policies, implement programs, and manage resources. Therefore, it is considered key to establishing the scope of the national governing body for sport and physical activity in the country.

It is considered that the most appropriate governmental status for the national governing body for sport and physical activity should be a ministry or a body with a high degree of autonomy and powers similar to those of a ministry.

In the case of Peru, the national governing body for sport and physical activity is the Peruvian Sports Institute (IPD), a public implementing agency attached to the Ministry of Education (MINEDU). The IPD enjoys technical, functional, and administrative autonomy in the fulfillment of its functions and has an independent budget. Its main headquarters are located in Lima, but its activities extend nationwide through its decentralized bodies.

Table 3. Basic Features of the Key Data Point

Key data Point	Value	Data	Fuente
Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Autonomous body attached to the Ministry of Education	2024	Congreso de Perú (2010)

Country's Positioning

The Peruvian Sports Institute (IPD) is the body responsible for the formulation, implementation, and oversight of sports policy in the country. In coordination with the agencies of the National Sports System (SISDEN), the IPD plans, promotes, coordinates, evaluates, and oversees the development of sports, physical activity, and recreation in all disciplines and categories. Its governing role ranges from school and community sports to high-performance sports.

Unlike other countries in the region that have opted to create a Ministry of Sports, the Peruvian model is based on an autonomous body attached to a sectoral ministry, which guarantees autonomy in sports management, its capacity for intersectoral coordination, and the creation of sports policies.

Peru's sports governance model presents both strengths and challenges. The existence of an autonomous body like the IPD, with planning, regulatory, and oversight powers, has enabled the development of programs and strategies aimed at strengthening the country's sports ecosystem.

Peru is making progress in consolidating its sports system, developing strategies to strengthen the stewardship of sport and physical activity in the country, thus ensuring its alignment with international standards and its impact on the population's quality of life.

Key Data Point 3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level

Key Data Point with Value

“Every education system should give due place and importance to education, physical activity, and sport, with a view to establishing a balance and strengthening the links between physical activity and other components of education. It should also ensure that quality and inclusive physical education classes are included as compulsory in primary and secondary education, preferably daily.” (UNESCO, 2015a, p. 3).

Physical education is an essential component of the comprehensive education of children and adolescents, contributing to the development of healthy habits, disease prevention, and the promotion of physical and mental well-being. The inclusion of physical education as a compulsory subject at the primary and secondary levels of education reflects a country's commitment to physical activity and the development of active and healthy citizens.

In light of the above, there is a clear need for data or indicators that allow us to observe countries' commitment to promoting physical education in the early years of life.

In Peru, physical education is a mandatory subject at the primary and secondary levels. It is regulated by the National Curriculum for Basic Education (Ministry of Education of Peru, 2016) and its practice is promoted in both public and private institutions. The established teaching load is three hours per week for both educational levels. However, since the subject is not completely independent of other subjects, the data value is "Partially."

Tabla 3. Basic Features of the Key Data Point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	2016	Ministerio de Educación del Perú (2016)

Country's Positioning

Peru has incorporated physical education as a fundamental component of the educational curriculum, recognizing its impact on the comprehensive development of children and adolescents. The National Policy on Physical Activity, Recreation, Sports, and Physical Education (PARDEF) reinforces this perspective by establishing guidelines for promoting physical activity in schools.

The Ministry of Education (MINEDU), through its ESCALE platform: Statistics on Educational Quality, allows for the recording and analysis of essential indicators of the education sector, including physical education. However, data collection regarding physical education faces limitations, which makes it difficult to accurately monitor compliance with the hours established in current regulations.

Peru has made progress in formalizing physical education as a mandatory subject in primary and secondary education, but still faces challenges in its effective implementation. The consolidation of monitoring systems, along with investment in infrastructure and teacher training, are essential aspects that will be strengthened to guarantee equitable access to quality physical education throughout the country.

Key Data Point 4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity

Key Data Point with Value

Legal frameworks are especially relevant for expressing fundamental principles and rights of individuals, as well as for making visible the priorities and scope of objectives, strategies, and programs. Hence the importance of having data on the existence of legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sport and physical activity. Likewise, it is important to ensure that these legal instruments are actually being applied in policies, programs, or actions with concrete results.

Peru has legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sport and physical activity. However, there are challenges in consolidating specific monitoring and sanctioning mechanisms for cases of discrimination in sports, as well as providing evidence of their level of compliance. For all these reasons, the key data value is "Partially."

Table 5. Basic Features of the Key Data Point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Legal frameworks exist to promote, enforce, and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sport and physical activity.	Partially	2003	Congreso de Perú (2003)

Country's Positioning

In Peru, from a general perspective, the regulatory framework supporting gender equality in sports is found in the Law on Equal Opportunities between Women and Men, which establishes principles of equity in various sectors, including sports (Law No. 28983, 2007). Within this framework, the Law on the Promotion and Development of Sport establishes the principle of equity, defined as "equal opportunities in access, retention, and treatment in the practice of sports in general and the integration of individuals into the National Sports System without discrimination based on origin, race, sex, language, religion, opinion, economic status, or any other condition" (Law No. 29544, 2010).

Likewise, the Regulation of Law No. 30432, Law that promotes and guarantees the practice of sport and physical education at different levels of education, provides that the Ministry of Education, in coordination with the Regional and Local Governments, promote physical activity and inclusive sport in the educational field, ensuring the participation of people with diverse conditions, including gender, age and health status, among others (Supreme Decree No. 007-2023-MINEDU, 2023).

At the public policy level, the National Gender Equality Policy (PNIG) incorporates within its guidelines the promotion of equal opportunities without discrimination, which is operationalized in Priority Objective 5: "Reduce institutional barriers that hinder equality in the public and private spheres between men and women," which includes the sports field (Supreme Decree No. 008-2019-MIMP, 2019).

Indicator 1. Percentage of the public budget invested in the national entity for sport and physical activity

Indicator with value

The budget allocation for sport and physical activity is an objective measure of the importance given to the sector in public investment priorities. At the same time, it provides a concrete benchmark for the scope of policies in terms of available resources.

A limitation of the indicator is that it does not record the budget for sport and physical activity allocated to government offices other than the national governing body. Therefore, it is desirable to generate a broader indicator in the future to more appropriately capture the amount of public resources allocated to the sector.

In Peru, the percentage of the public budget invested in the national body for sport and physical activity, specifically the Peruvian Sports Institute (IPD), was 0.08% in 2023, equivalent to 113,566,036 Peruvian soles. Additionally, 0.12% of the national budget was allocated to regional governments and 3.05% to local governments for initiatives related to sport and physical activity.

Table 6. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	0.08% Equivalent to 113,566,036 Peruvian soles	2023	Ministerio de Economía y Finanzas de Perú (2024)

Country's Positioning

The public budget in Peru is the State's primary management tool for efficiently allocating available resources. Through this instrument, the hosting of the Lima 2019 Pan American Games and the confirmation of Lima as the host of the 2027 Pan American Games have driven significant investments in sports infrastructure. Likewise, the Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF) promotes investment in the development of sports infrastructure at the regional level through Public Investment Projects (PIPs) and other financing mechanisms. These initiatives allow regional and local governments to allocate resources to promote physical and sports activities in their jurisdictions.

By 2025, the IPD, in coordination with the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the Ministry of Education, and PROINVERSIÓN, is managing the construction of 40 sports centers in 16 regions of the country, with an investment of more than S/ 600 million. These initiatives will be developed under the Tax-Based Works and Asset Projects modalities, with the goal of strengthening sports infrastructure and expanding access opportunities for sports practice nationwide.

The country has made progress in investing in sports infrastructure, which is essential for the widespread adoption of sports and the promotion of physical activity among the population. The implementation of these projects will improve access to appropriate spaces for sports practice, in line with the strategies established in the National Policy on Physical Activity, Recreation, Sports, and Physical Education (PARDEF).

Indicator 2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP

Indicator Without Value

Sport and physical activity have a significant impact on multiple sectors and economic activities. However, due to the lack of measurements or data records, their importance is not adequately visualized or identified. Thus, having statistics on the contribution of sport and physical activity to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) would help highlight their importance in society, understand their relationship with other sectors or economic activities, and inform the design of policies and programs.

The ideal source of information for the indicator is a satellite account for sport and physical activity due to its accuracy and the fact that it allows for an appropriate breakdown of the main economic sectors or activities related to sport and physical activity. However, having this indicator poses considerable challenges for countries due to the technical complexity of its calculation and the financial requirements for creating its data sources.

In Peru, there is currently no satellite account or data sources that allow for an accurate and disaggregated estimate of the percentage contribution of sport and physical activity to the Gross Domestic Product.

Table 7. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

Currently, there is no quantification of the economic impact of sport and physical activity on the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This lack of measurement limits the ability to accurately assess the economic contribution of sport and its potential as a driver of development.

However, the Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF), through Public Investment Projects (PIPs) and Budget Programs, provides an approximation of the investment that sectors, regional, and local governments allocate to sport. These projects make it possible to identify and manage resources allocated to sports infrastructure and programs in different regions of the country, providing a more concrete picture of public investment.

To address the lack of specific data, a viable strategy would be the implementation of a Sports Satellite Account. This statistical tool complements traditional national accounts, providing a detailed framework for measuring sport-related production, consumption, and investment.

The implementation of a Sports Satellite Account in Peru would require a thorough assessment to adapt it to the national context and the MEF's existing statistical platforms. This process would involve:

- Feasibility analysis: Studying the availability and quality of current sports-related data.
- Methodological development: Establishing a methodology consistent with international standards and adapted to the Peruvian reality.
- Training and institutional strengthening: Training professionals in the management and analysis of sports statistics.
- Inter-institutional collaboration: Promoting cooperation between government entities, the private sector, and sports organizations for data collection and analysis.

Indicator 3. Percentage of the population over 14 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender

Indicator with Value

Regular physical activity is one of the most important mechanisms for the prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, and several types of cancer. Physical activity is also beneficial for mental health, as it prevents cognitive decline and symptoms of depression and anxiety (WHO, 2020).

Therefore, it is essential to have indicators on the percentage of the population that is sufficiently physically active as a tool for diagnosis and policy design. At the same time, given the different needs of people and the inequalities that exist between them, it is important to be able to disaggregate indicators by age, sex or gender, ethnic origin, or socioeconomic status, among other criteria, to highlight the inequalities and challenges of inclusion in sports and physical activity policies.

In Peru, the percentage of the population over 14 years of age that is sufficiently physically active is 41.98%. However, given that the survey does not allow the indicator to be disaggregated by gender or age groups, and that it is very old (approximately 14 years), it is an indicator with important areas for improvement to comply with the international standards set by the World Health Organization (2020).

Table 8. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the population over 14 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	41.98%	2011	Own estimate with data from CENAN (2011)

Country's Positioning

In Peru, the data available to calculate the indicator dates back to 2011. It was collected by the National Institute of Statistics and Informatics in its National Household Survey, specifically in its anthropometric measurement module, in special coordination with the National Center for Food, Nutrition, and Healthy Living (CENAN) of the National Institute of Health.

The Peruvian Sports Institute recognizes the need for a new National Physical Activity Survey that updates this data by including variables that meet the anthropometric indicators necessary for international comparisons. This will be a valuable statistical input for the country, as it will allow for comparisons of the frequency and characteristics of physical activity and sports.

Indicator 4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old

Indicator with Value

According to the WHO (2022): “Physical inactivity is one of the main risk factors for mortality from non-communicable diseases. People with insufficient levels of physical activity have a 20% to 30% higher risk of death compared to people who achieve a sufficient level of physical activity.”

Indicators on deaths related to physical inactivity are among the most important for identifying the extent of the problem in countries and raising awareness about the benefits of sport and physical activity for health and longer life expectancy.

One of the most important, reliable, and globally standardized indicators on deaths due to physical inactivity is the one generated by the Global Observatory for Physical Activity (GOPA) in its “Physical Activity Almanac.” Although GOPA generates the indicator value for most countries, for some, such as Peru, it does not. Some of the reasons for not doing so are that the country may not have representative surveys on physical activity according to the standards established by GOPA.

Due to the above, the Peruvian technical team and the Consortium, following the methodology established by GOPA, conducted a statistical exercise, obtaining a relatively reliable and consistent indicator with those calculated by GOPA in its “Physical Activity Almanac” for most countries around the world.

Under these considerations, the percentage of deaths due to physical inactivity in Peru among the population over 18 years of age is 8.8%.

Table 9. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	8.8%	2011	Own estimate following the methodology established by the Global Observatory for Physical Activity (2021)

Country's Positioning

The last calculation for this indicator was conducted in 2018 by the Global Observatory for Physical Activity (GOPA). However, it is not possible to guarantee that this organization will be able to continue calculating this indicator in the future. For this reason, the Peruvian Sports Institute recognizes the need for coordination with health authorities to have tools that allow us to measure this indicator.

Indicator 5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education

Indicator without Value

“Physical education in schools and all other educational institutions is the most effective means of equipping all children and young people with the skills, abilities, attitudes, values, knowledge, and understanding necessary for lifelong participation in society.” (UNESCO, 2015b).

UNESCO (2015b) recommends that weekly teaching hours allocated to physical education be 120 to 180 minutes, depending on the grade level. “These hours refer to actual learning time in physical education only and should not include time spent changing clothes or traveling to specific facilities, nor time spent on other subjects, such as health.”

To have a reliable indicator, it is desirable that it be the result of a school census, or failing that, a survey representative of all primary and secondary schools in the country.

Currently, Peru does not have a data source with the above characteristics to establish the indicator's value.

Table 10. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

In the Peruvian education system, physical education is a mandatory subject at the primary and secondary levels, regulated by the National Curriculum for Basic Education, which establishes a three-hour weekly schedule for primary and secondary education (Ministry of Education, 2016). In this context, strengthening the monitoring of compliance is key to optimizing educational management and ensuring that students effectively access the benefits of physical activity.

In the area of physical education, it is necessary to improve the structuring and differentiation of specific data so that compliance with the number of physical education hours established in current regulations is more clearly reflected.

Indicator 6. Percentage of school students from 6 to 12 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender

Indicator without value

In the educational field, the effectiveness of sports and physical education policies must ultimately be reflected in the proportion of sufficiently active students, especially at the elementary level (typically students between the ages of 6 and 12), as this is where important lifelong habits are formed.

Hence the importance of having an indicator on the percentage of sufficiently physically active elementary school students, disaggregated by gender. Additionally, it is important to disaggregate the indicator between female and male students because female students have historically suffered greater delays compared to their male counterparts in multiple dimensions of development; in this case, sports and physical activity.

The ideal source of information for calculating the indicator is a student census or a representative survey specifically designed for this target population. However, in the absence of these, other estimation alternatives can be implemented.

Currently, Peru does not have a source of information with these characteristics to calculate the indicator.

Table 11. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of school students from 6 to 12 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

Measuring the percentage of students who meet adequate levels of physical activity allows for evaluating the effectiveness of strategies and guiding public policies.

While existing platforms such as ESCALE and SIAGIE have enabled the consolidation of a significant database on education, the current challenge lies in perfecting the mechanisms for collecting and processing information to increase the accuracy and differentiation of indicators. This will allow for a more detailed evaluation of the effectiveness of physical education in developing active lifestyle habits, as well as more accurately identify territorial and gender gaps, facilitating the implementation of differentiated and targeted strategies for the school population.

Indicator 7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs

Indicator without Value

The budgets of public entities and their objectives reflect the government's political and programmatic priorities. In this sense, they constitute an objective measure for verifying government efforts to close gender gaps in sport and physical activity. However, to have reliable indicators on the proportion of budgets focused on gender programs, these programs must have explicit and verifiable objectives and actions aimed at closing gender gaps.

Currently, Peru does not have data sources to estimate the percentage of the national sports entity's budget focused on gender programs.

Table 12. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

Gender inclusion and equity in sports are fundamental pillars of public policy in Peru, promoting equal access to resources, skills, and opportunities for sports development. However, there is currently no nationally integrated indicator that specifically measures the percentage of the budget allocated to programs to reduce gender gaps.

In the 2024 annual period, the Peruvian Sports Institute (IPD) allocated a budget of S/ 93,065,942.00 for high-level competitive federated sports, distributing it among 55 legal entities, including the National Sports Federations and the National Paralympic Association of Peru. This funding benefited a total of 28,865 athletes affiliated with the National Comprehensive Sports System (SISDNA), of which 37% were women (10,540) and 63% were men (18,328).

Peru is committed to strengthening the collection of gender-disaggregated data in budget execution reports. Incorporating this indicator into national records will facilitate decision-making, contributing to reducing gender gaps in national sports.

Indicator 8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity

Indicator with Value

Senior management positions in public and private organizations are where one of the most significant gaps between women and men is observed. Hence the importance of monitoring the gaps and progress toward gender equality in management positions in national sports and physical activity entities. This information will support better policies or affirmative action in this area.

Given the institutional and administrative heterogeneity of the countries in the region, the classifications used to identify management positions in national sports entities are not exactly comparable. However, by respecting the country-specific classifications, it is possible to obtain a fairly reliable overview of the indicator in the region.

In Peru, the percentage of women in management positions in the national sports entity (PMPD) is 22.03%.

Table 13. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	22.03%	2024	Instituto Peruano del Deporte (2024)

Country's Positioning

The Peruvian Sports Institute (IPD) did not have an explicit calculation of this indicator within its measurement system, so it was necessary to analyze the current organizational structure and identify the distribution of management positions by gender.

Currently, 30.23% of management positions at the Peruvian Sports Institute (IPD) are held by women, which equates to 13 women in management positions out of a total of 43, while 30 positions are held by men.

Indicator 9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old

Indicator without Value

There are notable differences in the level of physical activity between women and men. Specifically, "data show that in almost all countries, girls and women are less active than boys and men" (WHO, 2020, page 2). In fact, in most countries in the region, the gap between women and men increases significantly with age.

One of the most important goals of sustainable development is to eliminate gender gaps or differences in their multiple dimensions. Therefore, it is crucial that governments and the general public have indicators that allow them to monitor their progress toward reducing or eliminating gaps in physical activity between men and women.

Currently, Peru does not have a national survey that disaggregates the percentage of the sufficiently physically active population by gender and, therefore, allows for calculating the existing gender gap.

Table 14. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

Measuring this indicator faces limitations due to the availability of national data sources. Currently, the National Household Survey (ENAH) and the Demographic and Family Health Survey (ENDES) have collected partial data on physical activity in the adult population, but they do not include a specific indicator that allows for an accurate assessment of the adequacy of physical activity in people over 18 years of age, disaggregated by gender. In particular, the 2012 ENDES analyzed sedentary lifestyles and physical activity in the adult population, identifying that 45.2% of Peruvians aged 40 years and older did not engage in physical activity, with women participating less in sports activities compared to men.

Although these sources provide relevant information, they lack a standardized methodology for assessing compliance with the World Health Organization (WHO) recommended physical activity levels in the adult population.

The absence of a specific indicator in national surveys highlights the need to strengthen statistical measurement instruments for physical activity.

Indicator 10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities

Indicator without Value

The Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities establishes that, in order for people with disabilities to participate equally in recreational, leisure, and sports activities, countries must adopt measures to encourage and promote the participation of people with disabilities in sports activities, ensure that they have the opportunity to organize and develop sports and recreational activities, and guarantee their access to sports facilities (UN, 2008).

To implement the provisions of the Convention, it is necessary to allocate public funding to programs aimed at ensuring that people with disabilities have access to sports and physical activity. Likewise, it is necessary to invest in data and indicators that measure whether this objective is being met.

As with other indicators, given the institutional and administrative heterogeneity of the countries in the region, it is difficult to establish homogeneous budget categories across countries that can be accurately compared, at least in this first phase of the pilot implementation of the indicators.

Within the timeframe established for the pilot, in the case of Peru, it was not possible to generate information to establish the value of this indicator.

Table 15. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

The inclusion of people with disabilities in sports is a priority in national public policy. In this context, the Peruvian Sports Institute (IPD) channels resources for the development of adaptive and Paralympic sports, promoting the participation of para-athletes in national and international competitions. Measuring the percentage of the budget allocated to these programs allows for an assessment of the degree of targeting and equity in the distribution of resources in the sports sector.

In 2024, the Athlete Support Program (PAD) allocated S/ 1,530,550.00 for para-athletes, representing 18.11% of the program's total budget, while athletes received S/ 6,919,800.00 (81.89%). In terms of beneficiaries, 11.25% of the athletes supported were para-athletes (55 people), compared to 88.75% of athletes (434 people). Additionally, the National Comprehensive Sports System (SISDNA) registered 584 para-athletes (4.78%) compared to 11,630 athletes (95.22%).

In Peru, programs and financing mechanisms have been implemented to strengthen adapted and Paralympic sports. The main challenge lies in expanding allocated resources, ensuring equitable access and development for para-athletes. Improving the planning and implementation of sports policies will strengthen infrastructure, training, and competitiveness in the field of adapted sports, promoting greater participation of people with disabilities in the national sports ecosystem.

Indicator 11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population

Indicator without Value

People with disabilities are one of the population groups most disadvantaged in accessing development on an equal footing. Therefore, the way to verify whether policies or programs aimed at people with disabilities are effectively achieving results is to observe whether their physical activity and sports gaps are narrowing compared to the rest of the population.

To achieve this, it is necessary to have representative surveys on the physical activity level of the population with disabilities, disaggregating them by age, sex, or gender. This poses a significant challenge for countries because a significant investment of financial and technical resources is required to implement the surveys and subsequently the indicator.

In this context, in Peru, there are currently no data sources available to establish the percentage of the disability gap among a sufficiently physically active population.

Table 16. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

Measuring this indicator was not possible due to limitations in available data sources. Currently, the only database used to generate indicators related to the adequacy of physical activity is the 2011 National Household Survey (ENAH), specifically its anthropometric measurement module, developed in coordination with the National Center for Food, Nutrition, and Healthy Living (CENAN, 2011) of the National Institute of Health.

However, this module does not include the variable "disability" within its inference levels, which prevents disaggregating data on physical activity by this condition. Consequently, it is not possible to calculate the percentage gap corresponding to this indicator.

However, data from the National Comprehensive Sports System (SISDENA) reveal that para-athletes represent 4.78% of the total number of athletes registered in the system (584 para-athletes versus 11,630 athletes, out of a total of 12,214).

The lack of a statistical measurement system that includes the disability variable prevents accurate knowledge of the adequacy of physical activity in this population, reinforcing the need to update and strengthen data collection mechanisms.

The Peruvian Sports Institute (IPD) recognizes the importance of developing a new National Physical Activity Survey, incorporating the disability variable as part of its inference levels. It will also seek to ensure that the data collected meet the methodological and anthropometric standards necessary for comparison with international indicators.

Indicator 12. Percentage of government programs in health, sports, and healthy living that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence

Indicator without Value

Sport overcomes geographical, social, and political barriers; it connects people, communities, and countries; and, in this way, it fosters coexistence and social and political inclusion. Sport for development and peace is conceived as a social intervention strategy that, through the "use of games, physical activity, and sport," addresses explicit peace and development objectives. This perspective "incorporates themes such as gender equality, fostering peaceful coexistence, promoting tolerance for differences, encouraging inclusive behaviors, preventing conflict, and promoting health and well-being" (GIZ, 2021).

Based on the above, it is of great importance to generate indicators on the relationship between sport and the promotion of peace and social coexistence. However, at the same time, it constitutes a challenge for countries that must generate reliable information to obtain trustworthy, accurate, and transparent indicators.

In Peru, there are currently no sources of information available to determine the percentage of government programs that use sport as a tool for peace and coexistence.

Table 17. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of government programs in health, sports, and healthy living that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

In Peru, sport and physical activity have been recognized as fundamental tools for promoting peaceful coexistence, social cohesion, and the well-being of the population. Although there is no consolidated national measurement of the integration of sport into government programs under this approach, various initiatives aligned with this indicator have been developed.

The Peruvian Institute of Sport (IPD) has implemented strategies that incorporate sport and physical activity in different areas of intervention, with a significant impact on strengthening the social fabric and promoting healthy lifestyles. The main initiatives include: Workplace Gymnastics, Get Active with the IPD, Older Adults (Active Living), and Inclusive Sport. Although there is still no systematic measurement of the impact of these interventions, the initiatives developed reflect the country's commitment to the practice of sport as a mechanism to strengthen coexistence and social inclusion.

V. Findings and Lessons Learned

The pilot has been a valuable exercise, allowing for information mapping, identifying challenges, identifying opportunities, and preparing work teams for the general implementation of the indicators in the future. Based on the pilot implementation of the indicators, this section presents some of the most relevant findings and lessons learned documented during the process. Although the analysis focuses on Peru, in some cases it is conducted from a more general perspective due to its cross-cutting implications for the region.

- Although Peru has several national surveys related to sport and physical activity, the only survey that establishes the minimum number of minutes of physical activity, in accordance with World Health Organization guidelines, is from 2011. In other words, the survey is much older than the recommended five years. Furthermore, this survey does not allow for disaggregating information by gender and age groups. Overall, this is one of the country's main challenges in generating information that supports the development of the indicators.
- It is important that Peru strengthen its technical and administrative capacities to identify in detail the budgetary and programmatic categories through which the budget for sport and physical activity is allocated, and thus be able to generate budget-related indicators focused on closing gender and disability gaps in the population.
- Given the institutional and administrative heterogeneity of the countries in the region, it is difficult to establish homogeneous budgetary concepts or categories across countries that can be accurately compared. However, the pilot has identified areas of opportunity for this conceptual unification to improve the comparability of the indicators for their general implementation throughout the region.
- Generating the indicators and their sources of information requires multidisciplinary and intersectoral work teams. This, in addition to facilitating the calculation and monitoring of the indicators, also increases the capacity of the national sports entity to generate data and indicators to support policies and document results.
- Government policy measurement and monitoring capacities can be substantially improved through partnerships with academia or specialized research centers. In addition to their benefits for knowledge generation, such partnerships ensure a degree of continuity in the generation of information and the monitoring of indicators.
- Having reliable, regular, and relevant information and indicators requires investment from governments and society as a whole. Specifically, calculating some indicators requires allocating budgetary resources for the creation of new representative surveys, censuses, or administrative records, as well as for developing data collection, monitoring, and evaluation capacities.

VI. Recommendations and Next Steps

To implement all Ibero-American indicators and continue strengthening the country's measurement and data generation capacities to design evidence-based policies, the following recommendations are made:

- Establish a work plan to generate the indicators that could not be calculated during the pilot. The work plan should include work plans to identify and, if applicable, generate primary data sources.
- Implement the work plan as soon as possible to develop a nationally representative survey that will generate the indicator "Percentage of sufficiently physically active adult population," disaggregated by gender and population groups.
- Promote international cooperation mechanisms to share experiences, knowledge, and training, and to unify, to the extent possible, basic concepts on sport and development, measurement mechanisms, and administrative categories of public budgets.
- Establish an interdisciplinary and intersectoral working group (sports, health, economy, national statistics) to map information sources and indicators on sport and its impact on development, as well as to propose policies and technical criteria for generating statistical information on the subject.
- Design a strategy for tracking and monitoring the indicators, which, in addition to implementing the baseline for all indicators, includes an initial follow-up report to observe the evolution of the indicators. The strategy should also include preliminary targets for the indicators.
- Establish a working mechanism with a local university to jointly develop information sources for indicators, develop methodologies, and dissemination and learning mechanisms.
- Seek partnerships with international financial institutions or investment funds focused on highlighting inclusion gaps in access to sport and physical activity for women, people with disabilities, indigenous populations, and people living in poverty through reliable indicators and statistical information.
- Invest in the training and job security of personnel specialized in generating indicators and in monitoring and evaluating systems for the impact of sport on sustainable development.

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